

Rural development in Assam, India

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**Euro Afro Studies International Journal®
(EASIJ.COM)**

Email: editor.easij@gmail.com , editor@easij.com Website: easij.com

Published By

Abstract:

Rural development is the central subject of India like developing countries where 80% of people live in a rural area, the meaning of rural development not only the economic development of the rural areas, it also means that where each and every individual participating in the policy formulation and implementation take benefit of the public policies. In Assam is the gateway and centre point of North-eastern states. Assam has been playing a prominent role in the Indian economy, also cultivate the various type of agriculture facilities and mostly Tea, Rice, etc., The administrative system of rural areas 73rd amendment implemented, some tribal areas have run the tribal autonomous council, rural development means the whole subjects include like health, education and cultural all part of development, in this paper highlight the various scheme of government how far implement and people get benefit.

EASIJAccepted 1 December 2019
Published 6 December 2019
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3565901**Keywords:** Rural development, Panchayati Raj, public policy, socio economic,

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Introduction

Rural development generally refers to the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in relatively isolated and sparsely populated areas. Rural development has traditionally centred on the exploitation of land-intensive natural resource economics as agriculture and forestry. However, changes in global production networks and increased urbanization have changed the character of rural areas. Increase, manufacturers, and recreation have replaced resource extract on agriculture as dominant economic drivers. The need for rural communities to approach development from a wider perspective has created more focus on a broad range of development goals rather than merely creating an incentive for agricultural or resource-based businesses. Education, entrepreneurship, physical infrastructure, and social infrastructure all play an important role in developing rural regions. Rural development is also characterized by its emphasis on locally produced economic development strategies. In contrast to urban regions, which have many similarities, rural areas are highly distinctive from one another. Changes in global production networks and increased urbanization have changed the character of rural areas. Rural development as a concept suggests the overall development of the areas and sustaining improvement in the quality of life of rural people. It results in creating a 2 environment conducive to improve people's capacity and until the end of fully, without exploitation, on a sustainable basis. It is both the means and end of economic development of a country like India. Today, apart from governments, rural development has become a matter of interest to industrialists, financiers, bankers and philanthropists as well. In India, a country of villages, it means making the life of the majority, worth to live and thus paying back them the dividend of India's economic growth. Four decades of regulations and two decades of liberalisation, has made India the ninth largest economy in the world (World Bank, 2011), which could grow, second after China, at an average rate of 8.46 per cent, for the last five years, even in the aftermath of global economic slowdown (Economic Survey, 2010-11). There are predictions that if the current high growth continues, India will overtake Japan (pre-quake) by 2030 (Economic Outlook - India 2008 to 2010). Today India hosts 11 per cent of the world's richest (Forbes India Magazine 2010) and it is looking forward the fortunes to trickle down to the rural people. India has 6.4 lakhs villages with a population of 83.3 crores which is 68.84% of the whole of India (Census India, 2011). Providing timely and adequate cheap credit to farmers,

rural artisans, petty shop keepers, and micro and small entrepreneurs is of paramount importance. It is reported that rural India suffers from a more serious lack of finance than urban Indian (Bose, 2004, *Shah* et al., 2007, Mishra, 2008, Ramesh, 2003). Rural development strategies are a critical component of an inclusive growth

Objectives of The Study

- 1.) How does the capacity of poverty reduction Rural development institution role play?
- 2). To know various schemes made by the government of Assam for developing its rural areas.
- 3). To provide optimum measures for restricting rural-urban migration.
- 4). Changing schemes impact of people of rural area.

Methodology

In order to highlight the above objectives there is a need for define and various schemes, data, also so secondary method also use this paper, were collecting from books, unpublished journal, newspaper, government websites.

RURAL Development in Assam, India

Assam is one of the geo-politically large areas, Assam Rural Population census 2011 the total population of Assam state, around 85.9per cent live in the villages of rural areas. A majority of the state's population, almost 90 per cent of an estimated 22.4 million in 1991, live in rural areas where the mainstay of the business is production agriculture. In terms of the state domestic product (SDP), the agriculture sector contributed over 38 per cent of the state income in 1990-91. Assam Urban/Rural Population 2011, Sex Ratio in urban regions of Assam, was 946 females per 1000 males. For child (0-6) sex ratio the figure for the urban region stood at 944 girls per 1000 boys. Total children (0-6 age) living in urban areas of Assam were 450,807. Rural Development Department, Haryana The Department of Rural Development through the District Rural Development Agencies in implementing Special Beneficiary Oriented Schemes, Wage Employment Programmes and Area Development Programmes. The Government of India from the year 2000hasrestructured/modified

The Ministry of Rural Development consists of two Departments, viz.,

- 1) Department of Rural Development,
- 2) Department of Land Resources.

Broadly, the aims of the Ministry of Rural Development are: Providing livelihood opportunities to those in need including women and other vulnerable sections with focus on Below Poverty Line (BPL) households. Providing for the enhancement of livelihood security of households in rural areas by providing at least 100 days of guaranteed wage employment in every financial year to every household demanding it. Provision of all-weather rural connectivity to unconnected rural habitations and up gradation of existing roads to provide market access. Providing basic housing and homestead to BPL household in rural areas. Providing social assistance to the elderly, widow and disabled persons. Providing urban amenities in rural areas for improvement of quality of rural life. Capacity development and training of rural development functionaries. Promoting the involvement of voluntary agencies and individuals for rural development. Restoring lost or depleted the productivity of the land. This is done through watershed development programmes and initiating effective land reform measures for providing land to the landless rural poor. Path Behind Rural development implies both the economic betterment of people as well as greater social transformation. Increased participation of people in the rural development programmes, decentralization of planning, better enforcement of land reforms and greater access to credit are envisaged for providing the rural people with better prospects. Initially, the main thrust for development was laid on agriculture, industry, communication, education, health and allied sectors. Later on, realizing that accelerated development can be provided only if governmental efforts are adequately supplemented by direct and indirect involvement of people at the grass root level, the thrust shifted. Accordingly, on 31st March 1952, an organization known as Community Projects Administration was set up under the Planning Commission to administer the programmes relating to community development. The community development programme, inaugurated on October 2, 1952, was an important landmark in the history of the rural development. This programme underwent many changes and was handled by different Ministries. In October 1974, the Department of Rural Development came into existence as a part of Ministry of Food and Agriculture. On 18th

August 1979, the Department of Rural Development was elevated to the status of a new Ministry of Rural Reconstruction. It was renamed as Ministry of Rural Development on 23rd January 1982. In January 1985, the Ministry of Rural Development was again converted into a Department under the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development which was later rechristened as Ministry of Agriculture in September. On July 5, 1991 the Department was upgraded to Ministry of Rural Development. Another Department viz. Department of Wasteland Development was created under this Ministry on 2nd July 1992. In March 1995, the Ministry was renamed as the Ministry of Rural Areas and Employment with three departments namely Department of Rural Employment and Poverty Alleviation, Rural Development and Wasteland Development.

Rural development programme in Assam

In 1999 Ministry of Rural Development and Employment was renamed as Ministry of Rural Development. This Ministry has been acting as an affecting the change in rural areas through the implementation of a wide spectrum of programmes which are aimed at poverty alleviation, employment generation, infrastructure development and social security. Over the years, with the experience gained, in the implementation of the programmes and in response to the felt needs of the poor, several programmes have been modified and new programmes have been introduced. The Ministry's main objective is to alleviate rural poverty and ensure improved quality of life for the rural population especially those below the poverty line. These objectives are achieved through formulation, development and implementation of programmes relating to various spheres of rural life and activities, from income generation to environmental replenishment. In order to ensure that the fruits of economic reform are shared by all sections of societies five elements of social and economic infrastructure, critical to the quality of life in rural areas, were identified.

Health Development: Poor health indicators, 18 states™ including Assam were selected from the country with special focus to improve the health outcomes especially in rural areas through improved access to a decentralized public health system under the National Rural Health Mission (NRHM) programme in 2005.

Education Development: Assam rural education system comparatively very poor, the education percentage of rural area in Assam, 4,187,323 children (0-6) live in rural areas. Child population forms 15.62 per cent of the total rural population. In rural areas of Assam, the literacy rate for males and females stood at 75.40 % and 60.05 %. Average literacy rate in Assam for rural areas was 69.34percent

Drinking water: The department is entrusted with the responsibility of providing safe drinking water and sanitation facilities in rural areas of Assam., but most areas of Assam rural places are sour areas many diseases affected Waterborne diseases, such as Diarrheic, Dysentery, Cholera, Gastroenteritis etc. are most common in rural areas due to the contaminated drinking water associated with aerobic & anaerobic microbes. Similarly, vector-borne diseases are also comparatively higher in rural areas.

Housing: Many schemes were implemented since then. A full-fledged rural housing program Indira Awaas Yojana (IAY) was later launched in June, 1985 as a sub-scheme of RLEGP for the construction of houses for SCs/STs and freed bonded labourers.

Roads Development: The Assam State Roads Project is an Externally Aided Project (EAP) implemented for by the Public Works Roads Department (PWRD) through the Assam State Road Board (ASRB) for improvement of State Highways (SH) and Major District Roads (MDR) in the State. The total project cost is US\$ 400 million.

Electricity Development: Electrification in Assam the Power Department has taken up a number of initiatives to electrify rural all areas of the State under the flagship programme of RGGVY and DDUGJY. Under RGGVY, electrification works of 8348 nos. of un-electrified villages completed, 12841 Nov partially electrified villages completed, electricity connections to 1214398 nos. of BPL household are released at free of cost. Further, GOI has sanctioned 11 districts for electrification of 602 nos. of un-electrified villages and 37 nos. of SAGY villages under DDUGJY.s actinides cost sanctioned is Rs.317.86 Cr.

State	Total population	Rural population	BPL rate	Literacy rate	Government service	Death rate without medical treatment	Electricity beneficiary rate
Assam	31,205,576	26,807,034 (85.90%)	1,056.98	15,685,436 (69.34)	20%	9%	28.0

Under which Electrification in 75 nos. of un-electrified (UE) villages is completed. To impart greater momentum to the efforts in these sectors the Government launched the Pradhan Mantri Gramdoya Yojana (PMGY) and the Ministry of Rural Development was entrusted with the responsibility of implementing drinking water, housing and Rural Electrification Assam. The Power Department has taken up a number of initiatives to electrify rural Rural areas of the State, In Assam most of areas are riverbank where the electricity facilities not able to reach, government provide solar system in every house hold, during the Ninth Plan period, several anti-poverty Programmes have been restructured to enhance the efficiency of the Programmes for providing increased benefits to the rural poor. Self-Employment Programmes were revamped by merging the Integrated Rural Development Programme (IRDP), the Development of Women and Children in Rural Areas (DWCRA), the Supply of Improved Tool-Kits to Rural Artisans (SITRA), the Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (TRYSEM), the Ganga Kaylan Yojana (GKY) and the Million Wells Scheme (MWS) into a holistic self-employment scheme called Swarnjayanti Gram Swarozgar Yojana (SGSY). Keeping in view the needs and aspirations of the local people, Panchayati Raj Institutions (PRIs) have been involved in the programme implementation and these institutions constitute the core of decentralized development of planning and its implementation. The Ministry vigorously pursue with the State Governments for expeditious devolution of requisite administrative and financial powers to PRIs as envisaged under 73rd Amendment Act of the Constitution of India. On 25th December 2002, under Drinking Water Sector, a new initiative 'Swajal Dhara' empowering the Panchayats to formulate, implement, operate and maintain drinking water Projects was launched. In order to further involve PRIs in the development process, a new initiative 'Hariyali' was launched by Hon'ble Prime Minister on 27th January, 2003. Hariyali was launched to strengthen and involve Panchayati

Raj Institutions in the implementation of watershed development programmes namely IWDP, DPAP and DDP. Realising that empowerment of rural women is crucial for the development of rural India, a women's component is introduced in the programmes for poverty alleviation to ensure the flow of adequate funds to this section. The Constitutional Amendment (73rd), Act 1992 provides for reservation of selective posts for women. The Constitution has placed enormous responsibility on the Panchayats to formulate and execute various programmes of economic development and social justice, and a number of Centrally Sponsored Schemes are being implemented through Panchayats. Thus, women Members and Chairpersons of Panchayats, who are basically new entrants in Panchayats, have to acquire the required skill and be given appropriate orientation to assume their rightful roles as leaders and decision makers. Imparting training to elected representatives of PRIs is primarily the responsibility of the State Governments/Union territory Administrations. Ministry of Rural Development also extends some financial assistance to the States/UTs with a view to improve the quality of training programmes and to catalyse capacity building initiatives for the elected members and functionaries of PRIs. The Eleventh Plan saw injection of huge resources from the Union Budget to the rural and farm sector. This thrust formed the substance of the Bharat Nirman Programme. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act has provided a major foundational support. Department of Drinking Water and Sanitation has been separated from the Ministry of Rural Development from 13th July, 2011 and renamed as Ministry of Drinking Water and Sanitation. Schemes the following major programmes are being operated by the Ministry of Rural Development in rural areas, Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) for providing wage employment, National Rural Livelihoods Mission (NRLM) for self-employment and skill development, Housing for All : Pradhan Mantri Awas Yojana - Garment (PMAY-G) for providing housing to BPL households, Pradhan Mantri Gram Sadak Yojana (PMGSY) for construction of quality roads, National Social Assistance Programme (NSAP) for social pension, Sharan Prasad Mukherjee RURBAN Mission, Integrated Watershed Management Programme (IWMP) for improving the productivity of the land. In addition, the Ministry also has schemes for capacity development of rural functionaries; Information, Education and Communication; and Monitoring and Evaluation. A budget outlay of Rs. 86000 crore has been provided under the Plan head to the Department of Rural Development for the Financial Year 2016-17. An

additional amount of Rs. 9000 crores has been allocated at the RE stage to the department thereby augmenting the population to Rs. 9500 crores. Budget outlay of Rs. 105447.88 crores has been allocated to the department of Rural Development for the Financial Year 2017-18 and budget outlay of Rs. 112403.92 crores allocated to the Department of Rural Development for the Financial Year 2018-19 and Budget outlay of Rs. 117647.19 crores have been allocated to the Department of Rural Development for the Financial Year 2019-20. Assam Rural Population census 2011 the total population of Assam state, around 85.9 per cent live in the villages of rural areas. A majority of the state's population, almost 90 per cent of an estimated 22.4 million in 1991, live in rural areas where the mainstay of the business is production agriculture. In terms of the state domestic product (SDP), the agriculture sector contributed over 38 per cent of the state income in 1990-91. Assam Urban/Rural Population 2011, Sex Ratio in urban regions of Assam, was 946 females per 1000 males. For child (0-6) sex ratio the figure for the urban region stood at 944 girls per 1000 boys. Total children (0-6 age) living in urban areas of Assam were 450,807. Rural Development Department, Haryana The Department of Rural Development through the District Rural Development Agencies in implementing Special Beneficiary Oriented Schemes, Wage Employment Programmes and Area Development Programmes. The Government of India from the year 1999-2000 has restructured/modified most of the Rural Development.

Conclusion: This paper has outlined the current and previous years' government programmes rural development in Assam. Developing a modern rural development strategy for poverty reduction in Assam, And highlight the main point of intuition level rather than organization The Assam rural poor need to part references the development and implementation of the relevant policies and programs, which need to ensure education development, environment development, health , electricity, communication, small industries, agriculture, etc., and one thing lastly Indian father mahatma Gandhi says Village is the heart of country without village development India not able to reach the high stages.

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Cite this article:

Author(s), MONIKA MILI (2019). "Rural development in Assam, India", Name of the Journal: Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 48 - 60. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3565901 , Issue: 1, Vol.: 1, Article: 3, Month: December, Year: 2019. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

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